

Slovakia

This report describes the structure of the national higher education system in Slovakia, focusing on the institutional types as defined by national categories. It builds on the Eurydice Report on the national higher education system but complements it with quantitative information on the role of higher education institution (HEI) types in national systems, based on data derived from the European Tertiary Education Register (<http://www.eter-project.eu>) for the period 2011-2020.

Types of Higher Education Institutions

According to the Act on Schools of higher education, 2002¹, there are two types of schools of higher education:

- **University-type:** These institutions provide study courses at all the three degree levels- bachelor, master and doctoral. Only these schools are given the status of “University”.
- **Non-university type HEI:** These are professional institutions and generally provide first level studies only.

In terms of funding system, ownership and their seat², the Slovakian higher education system comprises public higher education institutions, state higher education institutions (military, police and medical schools) with seat in the Slovak Republic, private higher education institutions and foreign higher education institutions.

Main institutional characteristics. Legal status and the right to award a PhD

Table 1 below provides a quantitative overview of the main institutional characteristics by HEI type.

Table 1. Institutional type and legal status by HEI type, 2020

Category		N	Public	Private	Private government-dependent	PhD awarding
Non-university type HEI	Vysoká škola	13	3	8	2	11
University	Univerzita	18	17	0	1	18
Total		31	20	8	3	29

Note: Numbers reflect inclusion in ETER

Universities (*Univerzita*) are all public/state institutions and have the right to award PhDs. In total, about 60% of all Slovakian HEIs are Universities and equivalent institutions. Out of the 13 Non-university type HEIs (*Vysoká*

¹<https://www.slovakiaeducation.info/higher-education>

²<https://eurydice.eacea.ec.europa.eu/national-education-systems/slovakia/types-higher-education-institutions>

škola) most also award PhDs. However, in contrast to Universities, a high share of private institutions can be observed. The only two non-PhD awarding HEIs in Slovakia are the School of Economics and Management of Public Administration in Bratislava and the College of International Business ISM Slovakia in Prešov, both private HEIs.

Institutional history. Older and younger institutional types

Data on the HEI foundation year provide information on the history of Slovakia's higher education and its evolution over time.

Figure 1 shows that the expansion of the system in terms of the number of HEIs is relatively recent. While the *Univerzita Komenského v Bratislave*, the oldest of today's Slovakian universities, was officially founded in 1919 but follows the tradition of the Academia Istropolitana which was already established in 1465, only two more Universities, the Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava in 1937 and the University of Economics in Bratislava in 1940, were founded before 1945.

The figure shows two distinct patterns of expansion. First, the number (and size) of the different kinds of HEIs has increased in the time period just after the second World War with the foundation of eight HEIs between 1949 and 1959 including six Universities. The second wave of expansion started in the 1990s with the foundation of 19 HEIs, the majority of all of today's HEIs, founded between 1992 and 2006. This expansion included the foundation of six Universities in the 1990s and 7 of the 13, mostly private, Non-university type HEIs. This expansion ended in 2006 with the foundation of the DTI University and the Security Management College in Košice.

Figure 1. Foundation year of HEIs by type

Students

With 86% of the students enrolled in Universities, they are still the leading actor in the national higher education system. Complementarily, Non-university type HEIs enrol around 14% of the students. However, according to different institutional mandates, we also observe systematic differences between educational levels: Non-university type HEI account for about 15% of the bachelor students, 18% of master students (including long degrees), and 11% of doctorates.

Figure 2. Students by level and type of HEI, 2020

Note Total students include ISCED 5-7.

Personnel

People are a core resource for HEIs, as their competences are essential for teaching, undertaking research and producing scientific output. In that respect, ETER provides a rich set of data moving beyond the information available in EUROSTAT, which allows to analyse the composition of personnel by type of HEI and characteristics such as gender, nationality, educational field and, from 2020 onwards, levels of seniority.

As shown by Figure 3, there are major differences between Universities and Non-university type HEIs, as measured by total personnel in full time equivalents (FTE), and in the personnel composition. With over 20.000 FTE, the 18 Universities account for over 95% of personnel in Slovakia's higher education sector. As of the personnel composition, the share of support and administrative personnel is with 42% higher at Universities than at Non-university type HEIs (36%). Research and teaching assistants (RTAs) play a limited role in Slovakia and account for another 7% of personnel at Universities but less than 1% at Non-university type HEIs. This category is mostly composed of PhD and master students supporting research and teaching activities reflecting the different extent of research.

Figure 3. Personnel (FTE) by category and type of HEI, 2020

Since the data collection 2020, ETER also includes information on academic staff seniority level based on a classification jointly developed by OECD and EUROSTAT³. Combined with information on gender, this information allows measuring two critical issues, i.e. career prospects of academic staff and the so-called leaky pipeline, i.e. the fact that the share of female academic staff decreases systematically with seniority levels.

As of Slovakia, more than 2/3 of academic personnel are classified at the intermediate level while the share of both junior (6%) and senior (12%) personnel is much smaller. A reasonable gender balance has been achieved for junior (59% female) and intermediate (47% female) personnel, but only 28% of senior-level academic personnel are female (see Figure 4).

³ OECD (2022), Education at a Glance, Paris, pp. 412-413.

Figure 4. Academic personnel by seniority level and gender (HC), 2020

Financial resources

As illustrated in **Error! Reference source not found.**5, in the year 2020, Universities account for about 95% of financial revenues and academic personnel of the whole HEI system, i.e., substantially more than their share of students. This broadly corresponds to the fact that Universities also have an important research function. This difference is also reflected in the composition of revenues, where Universities receive a larger proportion of revenues from (research-related) third-party funds. Overall, state allocation remains with a share of over 90% on total revenues dominant for all institutional types in Slovakia, while student fees play a minor role for both institutional types.

Figure 5. Resources, academic personnel and total students enrolled by type of HEI, 2020

Figure 6. Composition of resources. Universities (Univerzita) and Non-university type HEIs (Vysoká škola), 2020

Changing roles over time

When observed through the lens of the number of students, data show a pattern of decrease, with the number of enrolled students decreasing by 31% from 2011 to 2020 and with a decrease of the share of Non-university

type HEI from around 20% to 15% of the students enrolled. However, since 2017, the total number of students remained mostly stable and slightly increased in 2020 compared to the previous year.

Figure 7. Share of students enrolled by type of HEI, 2011-2020

While also academic personnel decreased in Slovakia from 2011 to 2020 (Figure 8), this reduction of around 5% was much smaller than the decrease in students. As a result, the student to personnel ratio improved significantly. Like for students, the relative share of Non-university type HEI increased over time, however, Universities still play a dominant role in this respect.

Figure 8. Academic personnel (FTE) by type of HEI, 2011-2020

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